

nfdi.software Deliverable 3.1

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I. Introduction

To ensure connectivity and interoperability between nfdi.software and consortia specific marketplaces on the one hand and other basic services of NFDI on the other hand, WP3 aims to determine a common metadata schema for the description of research software. In preparation for the work on a common metadata schema/layer for nfdi.software, the goal of WP3.1 is to provide an overview of relevant metadata schemas (and available crosswalks) of the different NFDI consortia and of NFDI basic services.

The results of this deliverable are largely based on **a) a 2024 survey on research software metadata in the NFDI Consortia**, conducted by the working group on research software metadata within by the section RS Meta of the NFDI¹ and, **b) a 2025 survey carried out in the context of nfdi.software (WP2.2)**². Additionally, **c) further information on software metadata schemas and formats** used in other basic services was taken from publications.³ While the first survey gave us an in-depth picture of the state of software metadata within NFDI, the second survey provided a broader look on metadata schemas and vocabularies used. Additional research publications were taken into account to cover potential blind spots.

II. Results

a) 2024 Survey on research software metadata in the NFDI consortia by Working Group Research Software Metadata (NFDI Section (Meta)data, Terminology, Provenance).

We analysed the results of a recent comprehensive survey carried out by the Working Group Research Software Metadata (NFDI Section (Meta)data, Terminology, Provenance), published on 15.08.2024, as the starting point for our work.

Within the survey, the following questions address the matter of metadata schemas:

Question M1: “Which domain-specific metadata schemas for research software do already exist in your domain? If possible, please provide links to them.”⁴

¹ see Castro, L. J., Ferez, S., Hajiabadi, H., Kuckertz, P., Löbe, M., Schmidt, C., Struck, A., & Thiery, F. (2024). Results on a Survey on Research Software Metadata in the NFDI Consortia. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12704414>.

² see <https://github.com/KonradHoeffner/softwareurvey/>.

³ see section “References” of this document.

⁴ see Castro et al (2024), file “Questionnaire.pdf”.

Question M3: "Which generic-purpose metadata schemas for research software are used in your domain? If possible, please provide a link to them."⁵

As stated in the summary of the results, "(...) only a few domain-specific metadata schemas for research software were identified by the consortia, with generic metadata schemas such as CodeMeta, Bioschemas, Schema.org, and the Citation File Format being the most commonly mentioned."⁶ The results in particular provide CodeMeta, Bioschemas, Schema.org, Citation File Format (CFF) for M1, and additionally for M3, DublinCore, DataCite, DCAT and pyproject.toml. All results have thus been taken into consideration for WP3.1.

b) 2025 Survey on research software metadata schemas by nfdi.software

To check for recent developments, we cooperated with WP2.2 regarding a survey for needs and current implementations in NFDI.⁷

The 140 responses cover the entire spectrum of NFDI consortia and many affiliated structures such as basic services. For the survey (WP2.2), we contributed two questions that specifically ask respondents to mention metadata schemas:

- Question 1: "Which metadata formats do you describe your research software with (if any)?" with a multiple response option for CodeMeta, Citation File Format (CFF), Zenodo.json, as well as an option to mention other formats.
- Question 2: "If you use controlled vocabularies, ontologies or knowledge graphs to describe your research software, please list them below." This question was set up as an open question to give space for detailed answers.

The feedback for the survey section concerning WP 3.1 has been processed by filtering out dummy entries and summarizing the mentions of metadata schemas based on the originating consortium. This approach consolidates multiple entries into a single mention per consortium. Additional mentions and comments are listed below. The raw data from our analysis is provided in the appendix of this deliverable.⁸

Regarding Question 1: In the survey, CFF was specified 15 times, CodeMeta 7 times and Zenodo.json 8 times.

⁵ ibid..

⁶ see Castro et al (2024), file "Castro_Resulsts.pdf", p. 6ff..

⁷ information on research software within all consortia were collected by a survey of WP2 in cooperation with the Base4NFDI data steward for nfdi.software. All results in different formats such as CSV and Google Spreadsheet are available in a public Google Drive folder (<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1SLTh89soPV-35CeM7DEY2rhVzAa5gUBr>) and a Python Jupyter Lab notebook analyzing and visualizing the results (see <https://github.com/KonradHoeffner/softwareurvey>).

⁸ see also

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1MqBVL1kNqBBcTuogcewm8LsU792VzZ8HgMlfmAxPzmg/edit?usp=sharing>.

The following were also stated:

- R Package documentation using roxygen,
- Bioschemas ComputationalTool Profile⁹
- NeXus
- other discipline specific sidecar files, dep5, oer metadata"
- GHGA Metadata schema¹⁰
- RO-Crate
- DataCite
- Schema.org
- maSMP vocabulary

Our motivation for Question 2 was to explore the potential integration of software metadata into knowledge graphs, as well as its relationship to terminology services—both considered potential candidates for basic services. The following ontologies and controlled vocabularies/taxonomies were mentioned in the survey:

- ORCID
- ROR
- DCT
- EDAM
- Openaire
- TaDiRAH
- BRENDA Tissue Ontology
- Data Use Ontology
- Human Ancestry Ontology
- Human Phenotype Ontology
- International Classification of Diseases
- Mondo Disease Ontology
- National Cancer Institute Thesaurus
- NFDI4Earth Ontology¹¹

Additionally, collections of ontologies used in consortia have been mentioned:

- NFDI4CAT Ontology Worldmap¹²
- GHGA Ontologies¹³

c) Additional findings

Among the schemas identified in the results, several warrant special mention.

CodeMeta is an exchange schema for research software metadata, designed to facilitate interoperability and conversion between different metadata schemas. Crosswalks for several schemas relevant to the scope of nfdi.software already exist, and the RSD software used

⁹ see <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/ComputationalTool/1.0-RELEASE>.

¹⁰ see <https://github.com/ghga-de/ghga-metadata-schema>.

¹¹ see <https://nfdi4earth.de/ontology/>.

¹² see <https://github.com/nfdi4cat/Ontology-Overview-of-NFDI4Cat>.

¹³ see <https://docs.ghga.de/metadata/standards/#ontologies>.

within nfdi.software is already capable of providing software metadata in CodeMeta v3 JSON-LD.¹⁴

While both **RO-crate** metadata and the **maSMP Ontology** were not prominent among the survey results (both were mentioned once in question 2 of the 2025 survey), we consider them relevant within the landscape of research software metadata in NFDI since they are current efforts to establish standards for research software metadata beyond specific research domains. **RO-Crates** are structured packages for the exchange of research data. They bundle different aspects of research data - like methods, output/outcome, the data itself and software involved together - through linked metadata. An [RO-crate plugin](#) is already available for the RDMO instance provided by the DMP4NFDI basic service.¹⁵ The **maSMP Ontology**¹⁶ is a metadata schema for machine actionable Software Management Plans¹⁷. Version 2.1.0 was released in January 2024 and we will continue monitoring further developments.

Both RO-Crate and maSMP build upon existing metadata vocabularies, including schema.org, CodeMeta, and DataCite, and already incorporate many software metadata terms from broader or more domain-specific schemas mentioned by the consortia.

KG4NFDI explicitly refers to research software metadata and has mentioned the use of standards such as schema.org, Dublin Core, and DataCite for metadata mapping, linking, and integration. However, the role of Knowledge Graphs within the nfdi.software context requires further investigation. We anticipate that software metadata will be represented in knowledge graphs, but it may not be available in its entirety.

d) Limitations

Since the scope of both metadata related questions of the 2025 survey overlaps, we received some additional mentions of metadata schemas for research software in the replies to Question 2. We grouped those with the results for the first question (see appendix). For some of the ontologies named in the replies it is not immediately clear if they are relevant in the description of research software (e.g. NFDI4CAT Ontology Worldmap and GHGA Ontologies). Thus, further evaluation is required.

The landscape of Basic Services is still developing and most services are still in the initialisation phase. While research software as a topic is gaining traction, the focus within NFDI still is mostly on research data. Only a few proposals for basic services contain explicit references to research software metadata (schemas). Standards for research software metadata are still being established and have not yet been decided upon within all consortia. We see this as a chance for nfdi.software to collaborate early in the development of a service.

While we asked for schemas for research software metadata used within the consortia, the

¹⁴ see <https://research-software-directory.org/documentation/API/codemeta/>.

¹⁵ see Diederichs, K., Förstner, K., Hausen, D., Jagusch, G., Johannsen, J., Lindstädt, B., Schmitz, D., Schönau, S., Stäcker, T., & Windeck, J. (2024). DMP4NFDI - NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans (1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13445355>

¹⁶ see Castro, Leyla Jael et al. (2023). "A metadata schema for machine-actionable Software Management Plans". In: doi: 10.4126/FRL01-006444988.

¹⁷ Castro Leyla Jael, Giraldo Olga, Geist Lukas, Quiñones Nelson, Solanki Dhvani, & Rebholz-Schuhmann Dietrich. (2024). machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (maSMP Ontology) (2.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10582073>.

focus was to get a broad overview. More in-depth discussion about the role of the mentioned metadata schemas within the consortia is needed.

We assessed the availability of crosswalks for the metadata schemas mentioned in the two surveys and, in several cases, identified existing crosswalks via CodeMeta (see appendix). For some of these, technical implementations—such as GitHub Actions or Python scripts—were already available. A coordinated concept for exchanging metadata describing research software between the consortia and nfdi.software needs to be discussed with stakeholders to determine which schemas require additional crosswalks to be mapped and implemented.

III. References

- Castro, Leyla Jael et al. (2023). “A metadata schema for machine-actionable Software Management Plans”. In: doi: 10.4126/FRL01-006444988.
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